

THE VARIATION OF RELATIVE VISCOSITY WITH TEMPERATURE. ORGANIC SOLUTES IN NON-AQUEOUS SOLVENTS

BY A. C. CHATTERJI AND A. N. BOSE

A fairly comprehensive study of the temperature dependence of relative viscosity (η_r/η_0) of concentrated and supersaturated solutions of non-electrolytes in non-aqueous solvents has been made. The observed values of δ/η , ($\frac{\partial \eta_r}{\partial T}$) can be divided into three categories, viz. (i) having approximately zero variation, (ii) having positive value, and (iii) having negative value for the variation of relative viscosity. In majority of cases the results can be explained by Rabinovich's solvate hypothesis and the depolymerisation hypothesis of Applebey.

In a previous paper (Chatterji and Ram Gopal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **24**, 455) the variation of relative viscosity with temperature of aqueous solutions of electrolytes and a few non-electrolytes was studied. Several general conclusions about the variation of relative viscosity with temperature, based on the concept of depolymerisation of associated solvent molecules and on the hydrate hypothesis, were arrived at. It was suggested that these might be found useful in explaining further work on this subject.

In this paper attempt has been made to test the validity of the above conclusions. Moreover, this investigation is an extension of a previous work on the determination of viscosity of supersaturated aqueous solutions to supersaturated non-aqueous solutions, with a view to finding out the effect of viscosity on the release of supersaturation from such solutions.

The viscosity of non-aqueous solutions has not been very widely studied. However, important investigations in this direction were undertaken by Wagner and Mühlenbein (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1906, **46**, 867), Bramley (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, **109**, 10, 434), Kendall and Monroe (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **39**, 1802), Dunstan and Thole ("Book on Viscosity of Liquids", 1914, p. 43), Taimni (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, **32**, 604; 1929, **33**, 56), Briscoe and Reinhart (*ibid.*, 1942, **46**, 3, 387) and others. Most of the above workers studied the viscosity of the mixture and its variation with concentration.

Briscoe and Reinhart (*loc. cit.*), however, studied the effect of temperature on the relative viscosity of non-electrolytes and electrolytes in non-aqueous solvents and concluded that the relative viscosity decreased with temperature for all solutions studied except that of potassium iodide in glycerol. The concentration taken by them was not very high and, moreover, the solutions compared at different temperatures, though having nearly equal concentrations, were by no means exactly equal in concentration. For example in Table I of their paper (p. 389), the temperature increased from 25° to 60° and the relative viscosity decreased from 1.0355 to 1.0305 but at the same time the

concentration decreased regularly from 0.2427*M* to 0.2324 *M*. Therefore, the variation in relative viscosity could by no means be solely attributed to the increase in temperature. Further, no theoretical explanation was offered for the variation in relative viscosity with temperature both negative and positive. Whereas, in our previous paper an attempt was made to correlate the variation of relative viscosity with Rabinovich's solvate hypothesis and the depolymerisation hypothesis of Applebey (*this Journal*, 1948, 25, 39).

An attempt has been made to extend the above ideas to solutions of non-electrolytes in non-aqueous solvents in the present communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

Viscosity was measured in the same manner as was done by Chatterji and Gopal (*loc. cit.*), the modifications in the method adopted provided an arrangement for passing a current of dust-free air through the whole apparatus. The kinetic energy correction term, which is very small, has been neglected.

The results calculated from the viscosity data thus obtained are tabulated below.

TABLE I

Solvent.	Solnte.	*Conc.	20°.	25°.	30°.	35°.	40°.	45°.	50°.
1.	Hexane Naphthaline	15.66	—	1.223	1.226	1.218	1.221	1.218	—
		25.50	—	1.321	1.325	1.319	1.316	1.310	—
2.	.. Diphenylamine	9.83	—	1.258	1.241	1.241	1.228	1.214	—
		33.32	—	—	1.717	1.682	1.660	1.610	—
3.	Benzene Naphthaline	54.00	—	1.434	1.423	1.412	1.401	1.392	—
		82.00	—	1.541	1.540	1.533	1.516	1.503	—
4.	.. <i>p</i> -Dibromobenzene	75.60	1.358	1.357	1.360	1.357	1.363	—	—
		90.80	—	1.404	1.420	1.416	1.410	—	—
5.	.. <i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene	35.12	—	1.432	1.418	1.411	1.401	1.378	—
		66.64	—	—	1.867	1.837	1.811	1.763	—
6.	.. Benzoic acid	9.64	—	—	1.131	1.113	1.129	1.109	—
		14.48	—	—	1.206	1.211	1.202	1.191	—
7.	Toluene Naphthaline	66.00	—	—	1.498	1.495	1.498	1.477	1.473
		82.00	—	—	—	1.630	1.606	1.588	1.579
8.	.. Acenaphthene	24.50	—	1.321	1.311	1.293	1.290	1.290	—
		40.00	—	—	1.509	1.480	1.476	1.456	—
9.	.. <i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	182.50	—	—	2.456	2.366	2.310	2.260	2.213
		487.00	—	—	—	3.671	3.572	3.340	3.273
10.	CCl ₄ Naphthaline	28.00	—	—	1.279	1.268	1.252	1.238	1.229
		46.60	—	—	—	—	1.400	1.386	1.370

Solvent.	Solute.	%Conc.	20°	25°	30°	35°	40°	45°	50°
11.	<i>o</i> -Nitroaniline	1.998	—	—	1.056	1.052	1.050	1.046	1.041
		8.000	—	—	—	1.265	1.256	1.250	1.223
12.	CHCl ₃ Acenaphthene	24.200	—	1.637	1.596	1.560	1.518	—	—
		34.000	—	1.780	1.747	1.703	1.680	—	—
13.	<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene	33.320	2.068	2.022	1.975	1.929	1.874	—	—
		40.860	—	2.243	2.202	2.142	2.088	—	—
14.	Acetone Naphthalene	44.83	1.569	1.544	1.535	1.524	1.514	—	—
		68.00	—	1.780	1.752	1.731	1.721	—	—
15.	<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline	117.00	3.989	3.870	3.780	3.651	3.568	—	—
		280.00	—	7.453	7.200	6.873	6.630	—	—
16.	MeOH. Acenaphthene	2.25	—	1.030	1.010	1.006	1.007	1.006	—
		3.50	—	—	1.030	1.029	1.031	1.028	—
17.	Acetanilide	41.50	1.823	1.795	1.764	1.736	1.710	—	—
		64.00	—	—	2.226	2.173	2.117	—	—
18.	Benzoic acid	68.00	—	2.362	2.300	2.253	2.222	2.204	—
		83.00	—	—	2.613	2.563	2.512	2.448	—
19.	Diphenylamine	20.00	—	1.487	1.420	1.399	1.363	1.360	—
		89.40	—	1.827	1.780	1.743	1.726	1.663	—
20.	Urea	20.00	—	1.764	1.713	1.685	1.653	1.613	—
		30.00	—	2.240	2.135	2.090	2.040	1.997	—
21.	Propyl Benzoic acid alcohol	40.00	—	1.426	1.423	1.420	1.415	1.405	—
		56.00	—	—	1.699	1.586	1.570	1.559	—
22.	Urea	2.56	—	1.074	1.065	1.074	1.070	1.064	—
		4.00	—	1.124	1.126	1.123	1.116	1.110	—
23.	<i>iso</i> Propyl benzene alcohol	11.52	—	0.9186	0.9186	0.9760	0.9610	0.9616	—
		18.00	—	—	0.9472	0.9672	0.9699	0.9644	—
24.	<i>n</i> -Butyl Naphthalene alcohol	14.95	—	—	0.920	0.9204	0.9270	0.9250	0.939
		23.00	—	—	—	0.8982	0.8990	0.9060	0.9068
25.	Acetic acid	15.51	—	—	1.142	1.133	1.116	1.105	1.100
		36.00	—	—	—	—	1.159	1.137	1.128

* Concentration is expressed in grams of solute in 100 g. of solvent.

DISCUSSION

From the results recorded above the solutions can be divided into three categories (cf. Chatterji and Bose, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 25, 39).

TABLE II

Solutions giving approximately

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial c} \left(\frac{\eta_r}{\eta_0} \right)$$

Solvent.	Solute.
1. Hexane	Naphthalene
2. Benzene	<i>p</i> -Dibromobenzene
3. Methyl alcohol	Acenaphthene

TABLE III

Solutions giving positive variations of

$$\frac{\delta}{\delta t} \left(\frac{\eta_r}{\eta_0} \right)$$

Solvent.	Solute.
1. <i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol	Naphthalene
2. <i>iso</i> Propyl alcohol	<i>p</i> -Dibromobenzene

TABLE IV
Solutions giving negative variations of $\delta_t \left(\frac{\eta_s}{\eta_0} \right)$.

Solvent.	Solute.	Solvent.	Solute.
1. Hexane	Diphenylamine	11. Toluene	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol
2. CCl ₄	Naphthalene	12. CHCl ₃	<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene
3. "	<i>o</i> -Nitroaniline	13. "	Acenaphthene
4. Benzene	Naphthalene	14. MeOH	Benzoic acid
5. "	<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene	15. "	Urea
6. "	Benzoic acid	16. "	Acetanilide
7. Toluene	Naphthalene	17. "	Diphenylamine
8. "	Acenaphthene	18. Acetic acid	Naphthalene
9. Acetone	Naphthalene	19. <i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol	Benzoic acid,
10. <i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol	Benzoic acid		

Solutions of the First Category (i).—It was suggested in the previous paper that if the solvent consisted of simple molecules and the solute did not interact with the solvent in any way, the value of $\delta_t \left(\frac{\eta_s}{\eta_0} \right)$ should be approximately zero. When we apply this to the solution in category (i) given above, we find, that the two solutions, viz., hexane—naphthalene and benzene—*p*-dibromobenzene confirm the above conditions. But methyl alcohol—acenaphthene gives approximately zero temperature coefficient even though methyl alcohol is associated in the pure state, and therefore it appears to be an apparent anomaly.

Solutions of the Second Category (ii).—The solutions in the second category given above consists of the solvents (*n*-butyl and *isopropyl* alcohols) which are associated and the solutes (naphthalene and *p*-dibromobenzene) do not appear to affect the solvent to any appreciable extent as they are non-polar. Therefore, according to the generalisation drawn in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*) they should give a positive value for $\delta_t \left(\frac{\eta_s}{\eta_0} \right)$ and this is exactly what we find here.

Solutions of the Third Category (iii).—In group (iii) of the previous paper solutions consisting of simple solvent molecules and solutes forming easily breakable solvates with solvents were predicted to give negative value for $\delta_t \left(\frac{\eta_s}{\eta_0} \right)$. Whereas group (iv) consisting of associated solvents and solutes forming solvates, should give either a positive or a negative value for $\delta_t \left(\frac{\eta_s}{\eta_0} \right)$, depending upon which of the two factors, depolymerisation of solvents molecules or breaking up of solvate complexes, predominates.

As in this paper highly supersaturated solutions have been taken, the depolymerisation of the solvent must have been complete, and therefore the solvate effect predominates. The value of $\delta_t \left(\frac{\eta_s}{\eta_0} \right)$ at such a high concentration should be negative even in the case of group (iv) of the previous paper (*loc. cit.*).

For this reason instead of dividing the above solutions with negative temperature coefficient into two categories, we have put them into one. If we examine the group that gives negative value of $\frac{\delta}{\delta t} \left(\frac{\eta_s}{\eta_0} \right)$, we find that the system, mostly consisting of non-associated solvents and any solute, generally gives a lower negative value for $\frac{\delta}{\delta t} \left(\frac{\eta_s}{\eta_0} \right)$ than those in which the solvent is an associated liquid and the solute, generally a polar compound. But there are a few exceptions, such as toluene-*o*-nitrophenol, chloroform-acenaphthene, chloroform-dinitrobenzene, which give larger values of $\frac{\delta}{\delta t} \left(\frac{\eta_s}{\eta_0} \right)$ instead of low values.

On the other hand, propyl alcohol-benzoic acid and acetic acid-naphthalene give lower values of $\frac{\delta}{\delta t} \left(\frac{\eta_s}{\eta_0} \right)$ instead of higher ones.

Among these it has now been definitely proved that acetic acid molecules do not break up even in the gaseous state if the temperature is not very high, and hence depolymerisation effect should not play an important part; consequently the temperature variation should be small.

At this stage no definite explanation can be given for the other anomalies unless evidences are brought forward for the depolymerisation effects of solutes and their power to form association or complexes with the solvent molecules by quite independent methods.

Further work is in progress to bring forward such evidences by studying association and depolymerisation in binary mixtures by measuring the depression of their freezing points.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY,
LUCKNOW,

Received August. 4, 1947.